

Evaluating five EQ-5D-5L Bolt-ons for Atopic Dermatitis and Psoriasis: Psychometric Insights from a German Patient Study

Ines Buchholz¹, Laura Lübke², Carsten Spitzer², Alexander Thiem³, Clara Wülfing³, Fanni Rencz^{4,5}

¹Department of Medical Psychology and Institute for Psychotherapy, University Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf, Germany

²Department of Psychosomatic Medicine and Psychotherapy, University Medical Center Rostock, Germany

³Clinic and Polyclinic for Dermatology, Venereology and Allergology of the University Medical Center Rostock, Rostock, Germany

⁴Department of Health Policy, Corvinus University of Budapest

⁵EuroQol Research Foundation, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

Objectives: Inflammatory dermatological diseases are amongst the conditions in which the EQ-5D-5L has been reported to have limitations in capturing important aspects of health-related quality of life. EuroQol aims to advance a small subset of bolt-ons to become approved instruments. Among the candidates, three bolt-on areas – skin irritation (itching, IT), self-confidence (SE) and social health – are relevant for dermatological patients. This study aimed to investigate the psychometric properties of the EQ-5D-5L and these bolt-ons, including three variants of social health – social relationships (SR), social participation (SP), and feeling connected (FC) – in two prevalent conditions, atopic dermatitis and psoriasis.

Methods: An online cross-sectional survey was conducted in Germany from July 2023 to April 2024 targeting persons with atopic dermatitis and psoriasis. The survey included the EQ-5D-5L, five bolt-ons, and various disease- and symptom-specific patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs, e.g. DLQI, PHQ-4, POEM, PSS-10, PSSD, SSS-24). The following psychometric properties were analyzed: distribution properties, ceiling, divergent, convergent, and known-group validity, explanatory power of the EQ-5D-5L and the bolt-ons.

Results: Data from 180 patients with atopic dermatitis (mean age: 37 years) and 285 patients with psoriasis (mean age: 46 years) were analyzed. IT was more common in atopic dermatitis (90% reporting any problems vs. 74% in psoriasis). Problems with SE decreased with age in both conditions. Adding bolt-ons reduced ceiling most with IT (from 16% to 6% in atopic dermatitis and 19% to 11% in psoriasis), followed by SE in atopic dermatitis and FC in psoriasis (both 7%-points). Overall, 72% of atopic dermatitis patients and 54% of the psoriasis patients without pain/discomfort reported problems with IT. 40% of atopic dermatitis patients without anxiety/depression reported problems with SE and FC, while 29% and 51% of psoriasis patients without anxiety/depression reported problems with SE and FC, respectively. All bolt-ons showed good convergent validity with corresponding items and scores of disease-specific PROMs: IT moderately correlated with pain/discomfort ($r=0.52$), SE and social bolt-ons with anxiety/depression ($r_{SE}=0.67$, $r_{SR}=r_{SP}=0.52$, $r_{FC}=0.53$); correlations with DLQI ranged from $r=0.43$ (FC) to 0.65 (IT). Adding IT improved the known-group validity of the EQ-5D-5L (e.g., based on DLQI score and PHQ-4 bands), while other bolt-ons either did not or only marginally improved effect sizes. Adding IT to the standard EQ-5D-5L nearly doubled the explanatory power for the POEM (change in adj. R^2 from 0.245 to 0.474) and the PSSD (0.372 to 0.636).

Conclusions: In this German patient sample, IT performed best, especially in atopic dermatitis patients, with limited additional benefit from other bolt-ons. Among social health-related bolt-ons, SR and SP showed similar performance in both conditions, while FC captured more problems. Based on these findings, IT is a strong candidate for EuroQol's small subset of bolt-ons to be approved as a licensed product. Further research is needed to assess the value of self-confidence and social health-related bolt-ons in more severe dermatological populations and in contexts beyond dermatology.

Key words: EQ-5D-5L; Quality of Life; Psychometrics; Dermatology; Itching